

Urban Slum and Crime: A Case Study of Mammy Barracks Warri

¹Bada A.O., ²Onyemuze, B.N., ³Akharia O.O. and ⁴Simon-Eigbe, B.O.

¹Department of Urban and Regional Planning, Auchi Polytechnic, Auchi,

²Department of Humanities and social sciences, Auchi Polytechnic, Auchi, Edo State Nigeria

³Department of Architectural Technology, Auchi Polytechnic, Auchi, Edo State Nigeria

⁴Department of Quantity Surveying, Auchi Polytechnic, Auchi, Nigeria

E-mail afolabbada@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

Increased population and urbanization, a high child mortality rate, and aggressive urban development create problems that have an impact on economic growth, social development, and the financial crisis that supports the fundamental necessities and services for the urban poor. Uncontrolled urban growth, deteriorating infrastructure, human resource management innovation, and corruption are substantially to blame for the worsening of the accumulation of poverty, slums, security issues, and other environmental obstacles to urban progress. To collect quantitative information about respondents, 200 questionnaires were used in total. The questionnaire was supplemented with additional information gathered qualitatively through an in-depth interview and the snowball method. Using the random sampling approach, the questionnaire was distributed across the region, and the replies were examined using the straightforward percentage method. The effectiveness of government, economic and financial capability, social structure, heterogeneity, and poverty—both long-standing cultural challenges that affect security—have all been identified as elements that explain the implications of urban growth. While factors such as income disparity, cultural background, family circumstances, unemployment issues, education, age, gender, and race, among others, affect crime propensity, weak institutions, particularly the law enforcement agencies, technology, and other measures are being taken to address security issues and promote economic development. The study therefore suggests that the residents of the area be made aware of the negative effects of slums on both health and the environment, that CPTED strategies be adopted, that the existing area be completely cleared and redeveloped, though before this is done, the residents of the area should have access to alternative housing, and that the quality of life of urban residents be improved by providing jobs for the unemployed and young people.

Key words: Crime, Poverty, Slums, Upgrading, Urban areas. Transferred

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the most enduring physical manifestations of social exclusion in African cities is the proliferation of slums and informal settlements resulting from unsustainable urban development and urbanization [1]. Increased population, especially due to migration and birth rates, resulted in high densities, low living standards, poverty, social inequality, and increased factors in crime. At the beginning of the twenty-first century, more precisely in 2007, demographic data was decisively reversed on the planet: the urban population exceeded the rural population worldwide. Thirteen years later, 55% of the population lives in urban areas, mostly in developing countries [2]. Nigeria's urban population has expanded swiftly over the past 50 years. There is also an expectation that population growth will continue to rise in the coming decades. The underlying cause of rapid urban population growth and urban expansion in Nigeria is marked by its non-abating character and uneven distribution, with most of the growth being experienced. It brings significant challenges for states in a setting of continuing high rates of population growth, in which young people are deprived of socioeconomic structures to develop their basic human needs [3].

Significant changes in urban morphology and growth affect environmental aspects of the earth and have many implications for humankind and the global economy. It further engenders income and economic growth and is often underpinned by improved access to jobs, goods, and services, especially for the urban poor [3]. One of the important characteristics of the urban poor is that a large number work in the informal sector, where entry is easy and requires

less skill, less education, and less capital. Another interesting characteristic is that the urban poor do not constitute a separate world but are linked to the rural world through visits, remittances, social, cultural, and economic networks, and most importantly, through the recruitment of people from rural areas [1;4]

On a general basis, slums are developments that show attributes or characteristics of overcrowding, dilapidation, deterioration, and poor environmental conditions. Infrastructure, facilities, and amenities are usually inadequate in such areas. In simple terms, slums are areas of severe deterioration and obsolescence. Examples of infrastructure and facilities that are usually lacking in such areas include potable water, electricity, good roads, recreational grounds, and communication facilities [5]. However, the absence of adequate infrastructure and facilities endangers the health, safety, and general wellbeing of residents within such deteriorating neighbourhoods. In other words, slums are areas of serious environmental degradation that are characterized by absence of facilities and services that are required to make urban living meaningful [5;6].

In addition, many youngsters may modify their objectives to the reality of limits when faced with large real or perceived impediments, failing to address socioeconomic inequality in their surroundings. Thus, youth who reside in slums are invariably more likely to commit crimes and become victims [7;8]. Children and teenagers, particularly those who live on the streets, in informal settlements, or in underprivileged areas, are particularly at danger. Others include subpar projects for leisure and skill development, ludicrous awareness, and resilience as kids mature and develop, which encourage crime. Because there is no balance between crimes and their punishments, people choose to commit crimes primarily because the projected utility of doing so surpasses the remaining legal activity.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Study Area

It lies in the South geopolitical zone and is ranked the largest city in Delta State. Its geographical location is in the oil-rich coastal region of the Niger Delta. Warri has an estimated population of 942,683 million as of [9]. The city has a population density of about 7796.10 people per km². The population is spread over a total surface area of 369 square kilometers. Warri is positioned at the front end of the escalator of the rapidly urbanizing centre of social, political, and economic power in the Niger Delta [10]. The oil-producing status of Warri presents some peculiar issues that must be adequately documented as flashpoints for crime. In general, cities within the South-East and South-South geopolitical zones are prone to organized crime groups that traffic in persons and are also involved in drug trafficking, illegal fishing, environmental crimes, arms trafficking, maritime piracy, or tobacco smuggling, among others. The fact that many parts of Warri combine rapid, unmanaged growth with decaying public infrastructure means those risk factors can accumulate and deepen the potential for urban crime [11].

Mammy Barracks is an extension of the Nigerian Army barracks center in Effurun, Warri, Delta State. It lies between latitude 5°34'36" and longitude 5°46'23", respectively. The area is home to both military and non-military personnel and has a population of over 30,000 people dwelling in bungalows and congested buildings without proper airspace within buildings, making it the perfect place for hideouts for various crimes.

Mammy Barracks is an extension of the Army barracks situated in Effurun. It is meant to provide alternative shelter outside the barracks for soldiers and their families in the area. It grows and, in the process, ages due to misuse or lack of care, and without regenerative actions, it decays and falls into disuse [11;12]. Mammy Barracks exhibit evidence of decay in the form of poor drainage, the absence of toilets, dilapidated houses, and a lack of space. However, land use in the area was designed and developed for residential use by military personnel outside barracks; over time, this has changed and the narrative has taken on a new dimension. Generally, it provides for a range of deference accommodations for not only soldiers and their families but for people from all walks of life, without facilities like schools, play grounds, religious grounds, or ancillary facilities. Its development has emerged without formal planning in a haphazard manner, mostly through individual initiative and without any of the necessary infrastructure.

The numerous ethnic groups that cut across local, state, and international boundaries account for the dense or congested population witnessed in Warri and its environment today as an urban city. Thus, the Warri region developed not only into a well-known industrial centre in the south of Nigeria but also became a fast growing centre for trade and commerce. It has so much influence over the surrounding suburbs, including Effurun [13]. The surrounding regions are linked by industrialization, transportation, and communication and are connected economically and sometimes politically. Today, Warri is an industrialized region with available natural and human resources, most of which are oil and gas processing, a high level of incentives for workers by the multinational oil companies, available industrial spare parts, market forces, economic transactions at will, and many other potentials. These facts serve as motivational factors for people, including the criminally minded. In this regard, distinction in standards of living becomes a primary concern for people in the area, who are fortunate in their endeavors. But for the less fortunate, the low-income earners, or the have-nots, they 'stick' to or become prone to anti-social or criminal behavior so as to forcefully acquire the standard or status of the rich. In other words, materialism becomes the dictate of life [14;15;16].

Fig. 1 Map of the study area Locational characteristics and Google Earth Imagery of the study area
 Source: Author's modification from Google Maps and Google Earth Imagery, 2022

In this study, a case design methodology was used. In order to gather information from the population in order to draw conclusions about the universe's population of interest at a particular period, we can use a case study survey to get a snapshot of the population. In order to give research participants, the freedom to participate in the study, a semi-structured instrument was created. An observation checklist was created as described by [16;17; 18]. 40 adults from the community participated in in-depth interviews that took place at their homes or other locations that were convenient to them, in a peaceful setting, and in an informal conversational style. Traditional qualitative methods including in-depth interviews, focus groups, and some historical comparison studies are also modified. 200 responders from the study area were then chosen using a straightforward randomization procedure. The 200 local responders were chosen by the balloting process to assure randomization. The study collected data from both primary and secondary sources. With the aid of a standardized questionnaire, primary data were acquired. However, secondary data came from the research of other academics.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The present housing characteristics in the area give room for crime to be carried out easily. All of the houses in the area are bungalows, and the airspace between blocks is barely up to 1.2 meters, so there is high congestion between the buildings. Most of the room sizes measure 3.6 meters by 3.6 meters, while others are 3.0 meters by 3.0 meters. This agrees with the finding of [19;20]. Most of these rooms house up to five people in a single living space and are prevalent throughout the neighborhood. These structures are mostly shantytowns and are not fit for human habitation. In cases of rainfall, most of the roads become inaccessible due to the poor nature of the roads and housing in the area. There is a lack of proper sanitation, quality pipe-borne water, and most people defecate in their houses in bowls and nylons and look for places to dispose of them after usage. Since the location is tagged as a barrack area, highrise buildings are not allowed in the area, hence, the congestion continues and more illegal structures are constantly erected daily since it is a military base and town planners are not allowed to have control over the area. There have been developments in situational and social crime prevention strategies. Over the years, the Nigerian armed forces have been saddled with the problem of controlling crime. Major challenges militating against effective crime control rest on political, economic, social, diplomatic, and climatic conditions. The police are appraised to have performed below expectations due to the above-mentioned challenges and other factors such as cultural beliefs and practices, a lack of selfless service or patriotism, insufficient facilities, and poor remunerations. These challenges have a negative impact on investors, members of the public, and the nation at large. Many researchers have documented poor administration, technology, and attitudes among officers. Challenges that border on culture, environment, and logistics are trivialized. Crimes are prevalent in the study area, as Table 1 showed that 76.5% of the responses were affirmative in their decision, while only 14.0% said in the negative, with 9.5% having no idea as to the issues of crimes. Interviews with the respondents indicate that most of these crimes are perpetuated by youth, especially those within the age brackets of 12–35 years. Youth are the most sensitive, energetic, active, and productive citizens of a country. Through their creative ingenuity and labour power, a nation makes giant strides. Despite their creativity and ingenuity, youths are the most volatile when their creative energies are misdirected or channeled into disruptive endeavours. Hence, the prevalence of youth crime is a sheer disaster and catastrophe for any society [21]. The prevalent crimes in the area, as shown in Table 2, are stealing and robbery, drug abuse (which includes taking hard drugs that are not prescribed drugs), burglary into people's houses, gambling, influence into occultism, especially for teenagers, a high rate of tenant prostitution, fighting, as well as the prevalent increase in fraud (419) and internet frauding of unsuspecting victims.

3.1. Crimes and Causes

The issue of livability in the region has become very pressing of late, especially with the increasing environmental deterioration in the large metropolitan centers. It involves not only living conditions but also the issue of security in the region. Both in the rapidly growing industrial areas and the stagnating traditional centers, living conditions have been worsening over the years. In the former, there is a tremendous presence of population on limited facilities and this is manifested in the growth of slum and squatter's settlements around the area, over-crowded habitation, breakdown of waste disposal arrangements, inadequate water and power supply and generally poor environmental sanitation [20]. Also, the high level of rural-urban migration to the city of Warri consequently the town is characterized by a relatively high level of strangers, the presence of a large number of young people, the sometimes large number of temporary migrants and ethnic differentiation. One major problem associated with these characteristics relates to the fact that many inhabitants in the town integrate poorly with the new environment. As a result, there are high rates of crime, separation of families, increased instability in marriage and family life, conflict among ethnic groups and juvenile delinquency.

Urbanization is an indicator of crime growth rates as it growth to suburban area. The leading causes of crime in the area are majorly due to unemployment, poverty, family background, housing situation, nature of the area, loss of societal values, poor urban planning, income inequality, breakdown of law & order, high pace of urbanisation, corruption, educational background. The above agrees with the studies of [19; 20;21; 22], among who cited some of the above factors as the leading causes of various crimes in slums in various areas. Hence, it can be said that crimes in slums are caused by various factors, with poverty and unemployment acting as the leading factors. While factors such: crime control instrument has failed to some extent; Youth unrest and violence, armed robbery and car theft are the most common crimes and there is strong evidence of White-collar crime in Warri. The Socio-economic life of the dwellers is negatively affected by its increasing crime rate. Most crimes committed in Warri are committed by Youths within the age group of 13-25 years.

The level of crime rate in Warri is much higher than in the environs which are also smaller in terms of size, population land mass, industrial layout, and composition. Major crimes reported by respondents include rape, kidnapping, murder, burglary, fraud, terrorism, robbery, cyber-crimes, bribery and corruption, money laundering and so on. The study also revealed that residential burglary was particularly prevalent amongst middle-income residents. Gender-based crimes such as attempted rape was perceived to be the major challenge in the city and its common among the youth. The Nigerian society places great emphasis on material wealth and as a result, it's youths are becoming prone to deviant behavior which is the first step away from the accepted norms of a society or an institution. Urbanization, the worship

of money rather than honor and achievement, as well as the ‘copy-cat’ syndrome have been named amongst others as causes of crime among the youth.

Types of crime that have been identified range from petty – theft to violent crimes such as assault, kidnapping, abduction, affray, burglary, hooliganism, riot, robbery, looting, lynching, manslaughter, pick pocketing, mugging, hit and run, murder, rape, shoplifting, homicide, smuggling, theft, assassination, assault, trespassing, hijacking, and vandalism [21;22]. Their neighborhood is plagued with poor infrastructure like poor street lighting, water, sanitation, and health care. Companies, industries, and factories are not available, and this has somehow led to the increase in crime. This is because neighborhoods characterized by gross darkness and no access to electricity to light up the dark corners of the area increases the risks of crime perpetration. This low-income residential area and are plagued with the breakdown of social control in schools (dropout, vandalism, and insubordination), families (disobedience, fighting, quarrelling and stealing), and religious bodies (anti-social behaviour and activities), the focal point for crime breeding in urban neighborhoods. Individuals who commit crime are assumed to evaluate the likelihood risk of being caught and the associated punishment this factors have negative effect on crime rates. Deterrence, also known as clear-up rate has significant negative effects on all typologies of crime (persons, property and total). The implication is that a higher level of crime cleared by police and security agents is associated with lower expected returns from crime. This research found that demographic and socio-economic forces operating are factors responsible for making the neighborhood crime-ridden [20; 21]

According to respondents, the root causes of the challenges facing police is Colonialism and inability to traditional practices of curbed crime. There is no fear of the gods and the shame of being ex-communicated from the community for committing crime increases criminal behavior. The extorts money from the criminals before they are released without necessarily punishing the offender encourages the reoccurrence of such crime. Community experiences more crimes because the leaders shield criminals while others some of the prominent persons in the community are informants to the criminals [1;4]. The use of old and archaic equipment’s account for the numbers of poor operations recorded while criminals/bandits are upgrading both in skills and technology. Sometimes when pursuing a criminal and he runs into a compound, the people in that compound will hide him instead of surrendering him to the police. They find it difficult to give out information to the police when they know the criminals and when chasing a suspect, they get missed up in the crowd. Efforts in forcing the police to dismiss cases and spread wrong information about the police [2]. Apart from government, immediate community members are not providing relevant materials for public to curb crime in their community and people that diverge information end up being detained. Furthermore, police have “not so good” relationship with the public because of the unaffectionate disposition.

There are a lot challenges facing the in curbing crime among the public in the area. These challenges ranges from corruption, lack of funding, climate condition, poor equipment and training of officers. The has virtually abandoned its standards for recruiting staffs and this has disastrous effect on the masses. The now grossly compromised standards; this has resulted to widespread of abuse of established rules and procedures. They have become saddled with a very large number of unqualified, under-trained and ill-equipped officers. In summary, security agencies are loaded with undesirable workforce. Nigeria’s police force is over-centralized; it is under-resourced and ill-equipped. It offers from political interference with poorly trained and badly paid workforce that is prone to corruption and violence. These challenges have grave consequences on individuals, corporate bodies, multinationals, businesses and the community at large. This has led to relocation of companies from the environment.

Table -1 Presence of Crimes in the Area

S/N	Presence of Crimes in the Area	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1.	Yes	153	76.5%
2.	No	28	14.0%
3.	No idea	19	9.5%
	Total	200	100%

Table -2 Types of Crimes

S/N	Types of Crimes	Yes	(%)	No	(%)	Total	(%)
1.	Stealing/Robbery	179	89.5%	21	10.5%	200	100%
2.	Drug abuse	156	78.0%	44	22.0%	200	100%
3.	Kidnapping	86	43.0%	114	57.0%	200	100%
4.	Burglary	186	93.0%	14	7.0%	200	100%
5.	Gambling	143	71.5%	57	28.5%	200	100%
6.	Rape	61	30.5%	139	69.5%	200	100%
7.	Occultism	135	67.5%	65	32.5%	200	100%
8.	Prostitution	168	84.0%	32	16.0%	200	100%
9.	Fighting	167	83.5%	33	16.5%	200	100%
10.	Militancy	38	19.0%	162	81.0%	200	100%
11.	Human/ Drug trafficking	55	27.5%	145	72.5%	200	100%
12.	Fraud (419)/Internet fraud	174	87.0%	26	13.0%	200	100%

Table -3 Causes of Crimes

S/N	Causes of Crimes	Yes	(%)	No	(%)	Total	(%)
1.	Unemployment	192	96.0%	8	4.0%	200	100%
2.	Poverty	186	93.0%	14	7.0%	200	100%
3.	Family background	167	83.5%	33	16.5%	200	100%
4.	Housing situation	186	93.0%	14	7.0%	200	100%
5.	Nature of the area	143	71.5%	57	28.5%	200	100%
6.	Loss of societal values	152	76.0%	48	24.0%	200	100%
7.	Poor urban planning	135	67.5%	65	32.5%	200	100%
8.	Income inequality	143	71.5%	57	28.5%	200	100%
9.	Breakdown of law & order	173	86.5%	27	13.5%	200	100%
10.	High pace of urbanisation	133	66.5%	77	38.5%	200	100%
11.	Politics	97	45.0%	103	51.5%	200	100%
12.	Corruption	168	84.0%	32	16.0%	200	100%
13.	Educational background	174	87.0%	26	13.0%	200	100%

Source: Field survey, February 2022

4. CONCLUSION

Slums are run down parts of town having high concentration of persons living in small spaces with limited access to various amenities which makes life comfortable. The study has showed that crimes in slums are usually triggered by various factors with poverty and unemployment acting as the lead causes of these crimes. This has ultimately led to high social disorganization and has resulted in various crime rates ranging from robbery, illicit drug use, prostitution, juvenile delinquency among others. The study recommends various strategies that can help to curb the menace of slum if they are properly engineered and taken into action. We also recommend the expansion of opportunities for legitimate livelihood as this will help to bolster community resilience for crime prevention. Finally, we believe speedy prosecution of criminal trials is imperative for the dispensation of justice in the law courts of urban centres.

Based on the above findings, it is evident that the area is a modern day slum which is not fit for human habitation, hence the following recommendations are given.

- i. There should be proper awareness and educational campaign on the impacts of slums on the health and behaviour of people to help them understand the dangers they are in living in such a place as well as on the environment.
- ii. CPTED strategies should be adopted and this can be achieved through relocation of the existing citizens in the area which means alternative housing provision, then total clearing and redevelopment can be achieved.
- iii. The quality of life of the urban residents should be improved through the creation of jobs especially for the youths and the unemployed to keep them busy, since unemployment is one of the major causes of youth crimes.
- iv. There should be proper planning of the settlement again, and this time, the town planners should be allowed to carryout their jobs effectively through proper development control. These alternative development should make housing provision affordable for all with better living spaces which can also allow for highrise developments.
- v. There should be proper sactions and punishments for those who engage in various crimes, this would mean that corrupt practices among law enforcement agents must be stopped.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Agbola, T and Agunbiade, E. (2007). Urbanization, slum development and security of tenure: the challenges of meeting millennium development goal (MDG)7 in Metropolitan Lagos, Nigeria. Paper presented to the PRIPODE workshop on Urban Population, Development and Environment Dynamics in Developing Count
- [2]. Arimah, B. C. (2012). Slums as Expressions of Social Exclusion: Explaining the Prevalence of Slums in African Countries. United Nations Human Settlements Programme.
- [3]. Arun, K. S., & Karuna, R. (2014). Urban Slums: An Enquiry into Concept, Characteristics and Policy Interventions. ResearchGate. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/319988130>
- [4]. Arimah, A. C (nd). Slums as expressions of social exclusion: explaining the prevalence of slums in African Countries. United Nations Human Settlements Programme (UN-HABITAT) Nairobi, Kenya
- [5]. Atukunda, D. (2012). A Study into the Justification for the High Crime Rate in Slum Areas in Relation to the Laws of Uganda A Case Study of Mengo-Kisenyi, Kampala. LLB Thesis, Kampala International University, Faculty of Law.
- [6]. Carneiro, P., & Geraldo, J. (2000). Violent crime in Latin American cities: Rio de Janeiro and Sao Paulo. University of Sao Paulo, Brazil, Department of Political Science, Mimeo.
- [7]. Dung-Gwom, J., & Oladosu, R. (2004). Characteristics and Physical Planning Implications of Slums in Jos. Journal of Environmental Sciences, 8(2), 118-127.

- [8]. Ekpenyong, N. S., & Mathias, G. N. (2019). Urban Slums and Youth Criminality in Bayelsa State Nigeria: A Study of Selected Slums Settlements in Yenagoa Metropolis. *International Journal of Development Strategies in Humanities, Management and Social Sciences*, 9(4), 166-185.
- [9]. Ekpenyong, N. S., Raimi, L., & Ekpenyong, A. S. (2012). Urban Poverty and Juvenile Delinquency in Nigeria: Through the Lens of Port Harcourt Remand Home Inmates. *Research on Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(8), 127-132.
- [10]. Gbadegesin, J. and Aluko, B. (2011). The Programme of urban renewal for sustainable urban development in Nigeria: Issues and challenges, *Pakistan Journal of Social Sciences*, 7(3): 244-253. George, C.K. (2006). *Basic principles and methods of urban and regional planning*, Lagos:
- [11]. Humphrey, S. K. (2018). *Factors Influencing Crime in the Urban Informal Settlements. A Case Study of Kibra*. Masters Thesis, University of Nairobi, Department of Criminology and Social Order.
- [12]. Jeffery, C. (1971). *Crime Prevention through Environmental Design*. Beverly Hills: C.A. Sage Publications.
- [13]. Kruger, T. (2005). *Building Safer Communities- Reducing Crime Through Environmental Planning and Design*. CSIR built environment unit-sustainable human settlements. Pretoria, South Africa.
- [14]. McIlwaine, C., & Moser, C. (2007). *Living in Fear: How the Urban Poor Perceive Violence, Fear and Insecurity*. In *Fractured Cities. Social Exclusion, Urban Violence and Contested Spaces in Latin America* (pp. 117–138). New York: Zed Books Ltd.
- [15]. Moser, C. (2004). *Urban Violence and Insecurity: An Introductory Roadmap*. *Environmental and Urbanization Brief*, 10, 1-6.
- [16]. Nubi, T. (2015). *Institution Inaugural Lecture: Presentation at mini Auditorium*. Unilag.
- [17]. Ogboi, K., & Eze, H. (2013). *Enhancing Urban Security and Safety in Nigeria*. *Forty fourth Annual Nigeria Institute of Town Planners Annual Conference Landuse Planning and National Security*, (pp. 32-43).
- [18]. Oladosu, R., & et al. (2014). *Issues and Challenges of urban Renewal in Jos, Plateau State, Nigeria*. *IOSR J. of Environmental Science, Toxicology and Food Technology*, 9(1), 24-29.
- [19]. Oladosu, R., Bwala, H., & Muhammad, I. (2015). *Application of Physical Planning and Design Strategies to Urban Violence and Crime Prevention in Nigeria*. *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, 6(3), 1633-1642.
- [20]. Omole, F.K and Owoeye, J. O (2011). *Slum characteristics of a deplorable residential district of Akure, Nigeria*. *FUTA Journal of the Environment*, 6(2):94-103
- [21]. Rahman, M. H. (2014). *Juvenile Delinquency in the Slum Community: A Study on Tejgaon Area in Dhaka City*. M.Phil Dissertation, University of Dhaka, Institute of Social Welfare and Research (ISWR).
- [22]. Sani, A. (2013). *Landuse Planning: Tools for National Security*. *Forty fourth Annual Nigeria Institute of Town Planners Annual Conf. Landuse Planning and National Security*, (pp. 104-113).